

MULTI-RESOLUTION MESH-BASED MOTION ESTIMATION USING A “BACKWARD IN FORWARD” TRACKING METHOD

Gwenaëlle Marquant, Stéphane Pateux and Claude Labit

IRISA / INRIA Rennes

Campus de Beaulieu

35042 Rennes Cedex, FRANCE

tel: (+33) 2.99.84.25.44

fax: (+33) 2.99.84.71.71

e-mail: gmarquan@irisa.fr, spateux@irisa.fr, labit@irisa.fr

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a mesh-based motion estimation scheme for image sequences and nodal motion vectors optimization by using a multi-resolution differential method. Because our final aim is mesh tracking throughout a video sequence, neither backward tracking nor forward tracking is well suited. The backward tracking provides good results when simply applied to two successive images, but it is damaged by the initial mesh which can not generally be considered as known on the last frame. Likewise, forward tracking suffers from an analysis/synthesis problem but it allows long time trackings. The motivation of our work is to take advantage of both forward tracking (which enables tracking) and backward tracking (for its efficiency) in a “backward in forward” method. To illustrate the proposed method, first results concerning the motion compensation of a mesh are shown and compared to the usual forward approach for one single mesh level, with or without multiresolution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent development in video coding research deals with the use of a time-varying mesh for video representation and associated mesh-based model for motion description. A mapping function between two meshes is used to describe the displacement between two images. Such a mesh-based motion scheme allows to characterize local deformations between two video frames more accurately, that is, without blocking artifacts. This representation offers efficient compression and manipulation functionalities ([2]). Moreover, mesh-based representation can also be achieved object-based, as addressed by MPEG-4, which allows for content-based coding or manipulation.

This paper presents a motion estimation scheme for image sequences using a triangular mesh and nodal mo-

tion vectors optimization by means of a multi-resolution differential method, further improved by a “backward in forward” method. Experimental results will be presented to compare the tracking performance of forward tracking versus our proposed “backward in forward” tracking.

2 THE “BACKWARD IN FORWARD” SOLUTION

2.1 Classical motion estimation techniques for meshes

Two methods allow to predict deformations of a mesh throughout a video sequence: forward or backward mesh tracking. On the one hand, forward tracking requires the mesh at time $t - 1$ and looks for its matching position in frame t . On the other hand, backward tracking requires initial position of the mesh at t and looks for its matching position in frame $t - 1$. The choice between backward or forward node tracking deserves to look at the pros and cons about each method. A lot of mesh based motion estimation methods have been widely tested: various block matching methods ([1]), differential methods in forward tracking ([2]) and backward tracking ([3]).

Thanks to its easy implementation, the forward node tracking is the most widely used method in order to predict an image. However, this tracking scheme suffers from a main drawback: the analysis step takes place at time $t - 1$ and the synthesis step at t . In other words, the estimation aim is to optimize the reconstruction at time $t - 1$ even though we want to reconstruct t . Consequently, the reconstruction quality may not be optimal. Alternately, backward tracking makes it possible to optimize the reconstruction at time t . However, backward tracking involves knowing the mesh at time t and looks for its position at time $t - 1$. Therefore, in backward no tracking is feasible while keeping the same structure, un-

less all the sequence is available and the last frame can be considered as the one with the initial mesh, which is backward tracking back to the first frame. For all these reasons, we propose to improve the forward tracking by analyzing at time $t-1$ (as in the forward scheme), while optimizing reconstruction at time t (backward).

2.2 The backward in forward

In forward tracking, we aim at minimizing:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\Omega}^F &= \sum_{(x,y),t-1} (I(x,y,t-1) - I(x+dx,y+dy,t))^2 \\ &= \sum_{(x,y),t-1} (\varepsilon^F(x,y,t-1))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where Ω denotes the image domain definition or the object mask (cf.2.3) and $I(x+dx,y+dy,t)$ denotes the intensity evaluated at the pixel (x,y) displaced by the motion vector (dx,dy) at time t .

Alternately, backward tracking aims at reconstructing the current image t from the previous one $t-1$. The difficulty lies in the fact that implementing the backward tracking method supposes that mesh (t) is known. In backward, we aim at minimizing:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\Omega}^B &= \sum_{(x',y'),t} (I(x',y',t) - I(x'-dx,y'-dy,t-1))^2 \\ &= \sum_{(x',y'),t} (\varepsilon^B(x',y',t))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Equations (1) and (2) can also be written in the continuous case:

$$E_{\Omega}^B = \iint_{S_t} (\varepsilon^B(x',y',t))^2 dS_t$$

and

$$E_{\Omega}^F = \iint_{S_{t-1}} (\varepsilon^F(x,y,t-1))^2 dS_{t-1}$$

where dS_{t-1} and dS_t represent the surface element, that is to say one pixel.

Moreover, $\varepsilon^2(x,y,t) = \varepsilon^2(x'-dx,y'-dy,t-1)$. This implies that the integration over S_t can be accomplished over dS_{t-1} by a change of variables, as

$$\iint_{S_t} (\varepsilon^B(x,y,t))^2 dS_t = \iint_{S_{t-1}} (\varepsilon^F(x',y',t-1))^2 J(x',y') dS_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

where $J(x',y')$ is the Jacobian of the affine transformation between the two related triangles and is defined as

$$J(x',y') = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial x'}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial y'}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial x'}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial y'}{\partial y} \end{vmatrix}$$

Equation (3) looks like the computation of the error in a forward mapping, excepted here the Jacobian which

is easy to compute. Finally, equation (3) can be written in the discrete form (4):

$$E_{\Omega}^B = \sum_{(x,y),t-1} (\varepsilon^F(x,y,t-1))^2 J(x',y') \quad (4)$$

Compared to equation (1), the Jacobian J in equation (4) makes it possible to use backward estimation whereas the analysis is the same as the forward technique (cf. equation 1).

The Jacobian describes the infinitesimal area ratio of the deformed triangle to the original at point (x,y) . Consequently, it can be shown that $J(x',y')$ measures the ratio between post- and pre-deformations triangles. To conclude, nodal tracking algorithms are developed by minimizing the prediction errors measured over the original triangle at time $(t-1)$. Wang and Lee [4] used a similar change of variable with the use of a mapping function into a master element between the two patches to match. However, they concluded that the two Jacobians were equal, and for this reason did not use further the area ratio. Furthermore, we propose to integrate at time $(t-1)$ rather than at an other triangle that may imply sampling problems.

Since the Jacobian describes an area, it can be pointed out that this approach does not induce a complexity increase compared to the forward method.

2.3 Motion estimation method

In order to minimize equation (3), we use a Gauss Newton algorithm. Moreover, a multi-resolution strategy is used for taking large displacements into account. This is achieved through motion estimation over a Burt and Adelson multi-resolution pyramid (Fig.1) from coarse to fine level.

It can be pointed out that our error minimization only handles pixels inside the video object mask. This implies that motion estimation is object-based. Additionally, a constraint region ([5, 2]) is defined for each node to avoid mesh overlappings.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We compare the performances of forward and “backward in forward” tracking. All methods deal with an initial uniform triangular mesh. The visual tracking results are demonstrated in figures 2, 3 and 4. Frames in figure 2 represent the original Lena frame (considered as frame at time $t-1$) and an artificial warping of Lena (considered as frame at time t) generated for handling non-linear motions. The tracked meshes are overlaid on the original frame at time $t-1$ and the motion compensated frame at time t . Frames in figure 3 show the original mesh superimposed on the original frame at time $t-1$, the motion compensated one superimposed on the original frame at time t and the motion compensated one superimposed on the reconstructed image at time t .

Figure 1: Multiresolution strategy for motion estimation

	forward		backward-forward	
	mono	multi	mono	multi
artificial-Lena	19.02	25.27	19.14	25.40
Suzie	30.37	30.91	30.39	31.02

Table 1: Mesh tracking results for artificial warped Lena frame and Suzie (frames 51-52). Each entry gives the PSNR (dB) of a rendered video frame, using either mono-resolution or multi-resolution (three levels) motion estimation, for the two different estimation schemes. The entries are the results obtained at the finest full-detail level.

Frames in figure 4 show tracked meshes superimposed on the reconstructed frame at different time. The results show that “backward in forward” tracking is better than forward tracking in case there is complex motion in the video sequence, and at least equal if motion is simple. In the same way, this scheme is improved by making use of multi-resolution, especially to deal with large motion. To evaluate the performance of the multi-resolution versus mono-resolution motion estimation, and forward versus “backward in forward”, we measured the peak signal-to-noise ratio of warped frames with respect to the original frames. Different PSNR results for “artificial-warped-Lena” and frames from the Suzie sequence are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2: Tracked meshes are superimposed on the original frame at time $t - 1$ and the motion compensated frame at time t for image Lena with an artificial warping.

In our experiments, we do not ensure special condi-

tions for node points on border areas. In other words, we consider that if a node point lies on a corner or an edge of an image, it does not mean necessarily that this node has to stay at the same place or to move along the edge in the following frame: objects can appear and disappear in an image (zoom, background movement,...). Since the reconstructed image can not be predicted near borders, we build our mesh slightly smaller than the full frame dimension. Moreover, we compute the PSNR on a smaller area (10 pixels smaller) than the full mesh (because it can move from the image border and uncover areas).

4 CONCLUSION

Because backward tracking is not always feasible and forward tracking suffers from a few drawbacks, we have presented a novel solution “backward in forward” which allows to slightly improve performances of the forward tracking method. It amounts to weighted forward tracking thanks to a backward tracking approach. Results obtained show the relevance of the proposed approach. At the same time, multi-resolution estimation was also implemented and allowed to outperform mono-resolution motion estimation for all sequences we tested. A part of our future work will introduce hierarchical mesh tracking ([2, 8]) with further object-based results. We will also focus on the rate-distortion criterion [7] we have already introduced in our intra-frame research [6]. This criterion deserves to be taken into account while progressive/scalable transmission adapted to the available bandwidth of the network is topical.

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Figure 3: Tracked meshes are superimposed on the original frame at time $t - 1$, then t and the motion compensated frame at time t for the Suzie video sequence (frames 51-52).

Figure 4: Tracked meshes are superimposed on the reconstructed frame at time $t = 56$, $t = 63$, $t = 65$. It can be particularly pointed out the deformations of triangles near the mouth, the eyes and the general motion of the head.

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